

A RANDOMISED CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE DRAVYA SAMANYA SIDDHANT W.S.R AJAMAMSA WEIGHT GAIN

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is holistic science that works for healthy, wealthy and happy life. The wisdom of Ayurveda based on various theories and principles. The concept of “Samanya Vishesh Siddhanta” is one such basic principle of Ayurveda which helps to treat diseases. Samanya means similarity and Vishesh means dissimilarity, using this concept of similarity and dissimilarity many diseases can be cured effectively. Disease mainly arises due to the disturbance in equilibrium of Dosha, Dhatu, Mala and Agni, etc. The balance of these biological entities can be established using Dravyas possessing similar and dissimilar attributes. Mamsa rasa was prepared as per sharanghadhara Samhita and was given to consume voluntaries for the period of 30 days in group A and group B voluntaries were kept on vegetarian diet. Before to start the study and after the 30 days duration weight and BMI were recorded. In both the group. It was observed that mamsa rasa consumed group there was increase in the mean weight as well compared to another group after the study it was significant.

KEYWORDS: Samanyavisheshsiddhanth, Dravyasamnyasiddhanth, Ajamamsa rasa.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is science of which gives knowledge of life and healthy regimen. Ayurveda not only prevents and treats diseases but also maintain mental, physical and spiritual health. The balancing state of Doshas, Dhatus Agni and Malas is responsible for normal health status while imbalance leads pathological manifestation. Ayurveda described many siddhantas (principles) for maintaining and promoting general health. These Siddhantas (principles) are Panchamahabhut siddhant,^[1] Triguna Siddhant^[2] and Samanya Vishesha Siddhanta^[3] etc. Amongst these siddhantas (principles) the Samanya Vishesha Siddhanth is important one. This Siddhanth (Principle) mainly based on the concept of similarity and dissimilarity which helps to attain equilibrium of Dosha, Dhatu and Mala, etc.

Samanya Vishesh Siddhanta based on the qualities of substances which either increases or decreases quality and quantity of Bhavpadarth (Dravya, Guna and Karma) The word samanya denotes **growth** in Bhavpadarth (Dravya, Guna and Karma) while Vishesh denotes **destruction** in Bhavpadarth (Dravya, Guna and Karma). The motive behind this growth or **depletion** of Bhavpadarth (Dravya, Guna and Karma) is to achieve original Prakruti or **depletion** of Bhavpadarth (Dravya, Guna and Karma) is to achieve original Prakruti or state of equilibrium. This concept used in Chikitsa since Aushadhis of same and opposite quality can help to potentiate and pacify Doshas respectively.

Ayurveda Acharyas classified Samanya in different ways and Acharya Charaka has classified into 3 types Dravya samanya^[4] means consuming the same Dravya say for example consumption of Mamsa (meat) increases mamsadhatu (Muscle mass). Guna means **Properties (qualities)** for example consumption of milk and ghee improves state of shukra dhatu (sperm count) since milk and ghee have same gunas as that of shukra dhatu.^[5] Karma samanya means action or conduction that will increase same quality example- sleeping increases kapha since nidra as a karma possesses predominant of kapha.^[6]

An attempt was made with this clinical study to evaluate Dravya samanya siddhanta mentioned by Acharya Charaka in sutra sthana 1st chapter Deeraghanjiviteeya adhyaya with the example Aja mamsa rasa (goat meat soup). As Ajamamsa rasa will increase the mamsa dhatu in the body (muscular mass) which is certainly responsible to increase in weight of body.

AIM & OBJECTIVES

To validate the Dravya samanya principle and to provide evidence.

MATERIAL & METHODS

1. Pharmaceutical Study^[7]

Materials: Aja mamsa, jala, containers, gas stove.

Method: Ajamamsa was purchased from the market wash with clean water. Cleaned mamsa & water both were taken in 1: 6 Ratio in container and boiled on low flame and mamsa rasa is prepared. Thus, prepared mamsa rasa was used for clinical study. Every day preparation was carried out and used in fresh condition. It was not stored & preserved.

2. Clinical Study

Materials & methods

Materials: Patients from R P Karadi hospital Ilkal and Aja mamsa rasa both were framed the materials.

Method: Clinical study was carried out with IEC approval letter with reference number SVMAMC/Ethical/335/2022-23. Dated on 15/11/23.

Group: A were served the normal diet and instructed to not to consume any non vegetarian food during the period of 30 days.

Group: B were served with 100 ml of Ajamamsa rasa prepared in pharmacy daily for 30 days Mamsa rasa prepared according to Bhaisjya Kalpana by Shobha Hiremath^[8] i.e 6 pala of Mamsa with 1 prastajala.

Selection of patients was based on following inclusion&exclusion criteria Randomly selected patients were divided in to two groups.

Inclusion criteria: 1 Age between 18-30 years. 2. Male participants.

Exclusion criteria: 1. Age below 18 and above 30 years, 2. Female participants, 3. Chronic and systemic disorders obesity etc.

Assessment parameters

Before & after 30 days duration weight and height were measured on the basis of BMI.^[9]

OBSERVATIONS & RESULTS

Table no 3: Shows: overall results of the study compared statistically before & after clinical trials.

Group	Variables	Assessment	Mean	Mean Diff.	%	SD	Wilcoxon signed-rank test Value	p-value	Remarks
A	Weight	BT	59.06			27.46			
		AT	51.347	7.713	13.059	4.699	72	0.011	Significant
		EF	51.347	7.713	13.059	4.699	72	0.011	Significant
	BMI	BT	18.393			1.439			
		AT	18.167	0.226	1.23	1.322	55.5	0.05	Significant
		EF	18.167	0.226	1.23	1.322	55.5	0.05	Significant
B	Weight	BT	51.773			5.59			
		AT	53.493	-1.72	-3.32	5.33	0	< .001	Significant
		EF	53.63	-1.857	-3.32	5.216	0	< .001	Significant
	BMI	BT	18.113			1.923			
		AT	18.7	-0.587	-3.240	1.812	0	< .001	Significant
		EF	18.8	-0.687	-3.792	1.781	0	< .001	Significant

DISCUSSION

The word Siddhantas has different meanings based on contexts Shastra or science point of view it may be considered as established theory in ayurveda such many siddhantas one may find among those samanyavishesha siddhanta is one further this siddhanta is sub classified it to 3 types guna samanya, Dravya samanya and karma samanya. In present study Dravya samanya was verified by clinical trial.

Ajamamsa rasa is prepared according to method mentioned in sharanghadhara Samhita. method. 1 part of Ajamamsa which was cleaned properly later on added 6 parts of water and boiled till complete mamsa boils. Further only mamsa rasa was collected and used for the study.

In the clinical present study voluntaries were randomly selected and divided in to two groups. In the group A treated with normal vegetarian diet and in group B served with Ajamamsa rasa prepared as per classical method. Before to start the study and after completion of 30day period weight & BMI calculated & compared.

In group A mean weight before the study was 59.06 after study was 51.74 and BMI before the study was 18.39 And after study was 18.16.

In group B mean weight before the study was 51.77 after study was 53.63 BMI before the study was 18.11 and after study was 18.8.

After comparing the mean weight results of both groups it showed that group which received mamsa rasa has increased weight as well as BMI too noted.

Samanya siddhanta itself explains similar properties will increase similar bhava. In this study in group A voluntaries consumed mamsa rasa was the reason that increase in weight was noted. Where as in another group voluntaries consumed vegetarian diet & were completely kept away from non veg food. Increase in weight was not noted in comparison with the previous group. Thus, this study become an evidence base for the samanya siddhanta explained in Ayurveda.

CONCLUSION

Dravya samanya explains that the when drugs having similar properties are consumed, they will increase the dhatu in the body which too possess similar properties. Like consuming Mamsa rasa daily leads to increase in Mamsa dhatu i.e muscle mass leading to increase in weight. Based on this siddhanta and to verify these 30 randomly selected patients were selected from R.P.karadi hospital divided into A and B groups. A group treated with normal vegetarian diet prepared by following classical method and B group treated with Mamsarasa prepared by classical method. After completing the study duration weight and height measurements were noted and BMI was calculated. Results showed increased in weight in group B compared to group A. Thus, study has provided valid data and established that Dravya samanya siddhanta is correct.

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